

DEVELOPMENT AND APPLICATIONS OF CARBON NANOTUBE NANOCOMPOSITES

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1. Introduction

The excellent mechanical, electrical and chemical properties support carbon nanotubes (CNTs) as an ideal fillers in composite materials. Many researchers have attempted to fabricate carbon nanotube nanocomposites by means of traditional fabrication process, which consists of mixing CNTs with matrix powders followed by sintering or hot pressing [1, 2]. However, most of these attempts were not successful to fabricate carbon nanotube nanocomposites with homogeneously dispersed CNTs in matrices. This is mainly due to strong agglomeration of CNTs since the van der Waals' force between CNTs causes them to mutually attract

each other rather to form aggregates in matrices. In order to overcome the poor dispersion, molecular-level mixing process has been suggested for homogeneous dispersion of CNTs with strong bonding at CNT/matrix interface [3, 4]. The molecular level mixing process consists of 4 steps, functionalization of CNTs, bonding matrix ions on CNTs, nucleation/growth and oxidation/reduction, as shown in Fig.1.

In this research, multi-functional CNT/Inorganic or CNT/Organic nanocomposites are fabricated by molecular-level mixing process and characterized their mechanical, optoelectronic and electrochemical properties for structural and functional applications.

Fig 1. Schematics depicting strategies and procedures for the molecular-level mixing process. (a) Functionalization of CNT, (b) reaction between the ions and the functional group on the CNT surface, (c) nucleation and growth of matrix particles by reduction or solvent evaporation and (d) CNT/Inorganic nanocomposite powders in which CNTs are homogeneously implanted.

2. CNT/Inorganic Nanocomposites for Structural Applications

Molecular-level mixing process produces various types of CNT/Inorganic nanocomposite powders. The CNTs are embedded within the inorganic powders (Fig.2(a),(d)) or the matrix phase beads are formed along CNTs (Fig.2(b)). Otherwise, CNTs are fully coated with the matrix phase (Fig.2(c)). The most important feature in this process is that CNTs and matrix ions are mixed homogeneously each other at molecular level. The morphologies of the CNT/Inorganic nanocomposite powders show an ideal composite microstructure, which display that CNTs are homogeneously mixed with the matrix powders. The CNT/Inorganic nanocomposite powders were consolidated into bulk CNT/Inorganic with full densification. The consolidated CNT/Cu and CNT/Co nanocomposites show homogeneous distribution of CNTs within the matrices (Fig.3).

Fig.2 SEM morphology of CNT/Inorganic nanocomposite powders. (a) CNT/Cu nanocomposite powders, (b) CNT/Ni nanocomposite powders, (c) CNT/Co nanocomposite powders [5] and (d) CNT/Al₂O₃ nanocomposite powders [6].

The mechanical properties of CNT/Cu nanocomposite were characterized by compressive test. Fig.4 shows that the yield strengths of CNT/Cu nanocomposites are much higher than that of Cu, which is fabricated by the same process. Owing to the reinforcing effect of CNT, 5 vol.% CNT/Cu nanocomposite shows the excellent yield strength of 360 MPa, which is 2.3 times higher than that of Cu. Especially, in the 10 vol.% CNT/Cu, the yield strength is 485 MPa, which is more than 3 times

larger than that of Cu. In addition, it was also found that Young's modulus of CNT/Cu nanocomposite increases with increasing the volume fraction of carbon nanotubes as observed in Fig.4(b).

Fig.3 SEM micrographs showing homogeneous distribution of CNT in (a) 5 vol.% CNT/Cu and (b) 7 vol.% CNT/Co.

Fig.4 Mechanical properties of CNT/Cu nanocomposites. (a) Stress-strain curves of CNT/Cu nanocomposites obtained by compressive test, (b) yield strength and Young's modulus of CNT/Cu nanocomposites with varying the volume fraction of CNTs [3].

The mechanical properties of CNT/Ni nanocomposites are shown in Fig.5. Hardness of 5 vol.% CNT/Ni nanocomposite was 287 Hv and 10 vol.% CNT/Ni nanocomposite was 403 Hv, which increase 17 and 63% from that of Ni, respectively.

The increase of hardness by addition of CNTs is supposed to both the grain refinement effect and the composite strengthening effect of CNTs. The yield strength of CNT/Ni nanocomposites increase with increasing the MWNTs volume fraction. The yield strength of 5 vol.% CNTs/Ni was 723 MPa, 1.6 times increases compare to Ni while the yield strength of 10 vol.% CNTs/Ni nanocomposites was 1329 MPa, 3times increases compared to Ni.

The remarkable strengthening phenomenon by CNT was due to a high load-transfer efficiency of CNTs in matrix and high load-transfer caused by strong interfacial bonding between CNTs and matrix during the molecular-level mixing process [3, 4].

Fig. 5 Mechanical properties of CNT/Ni nanocomposites. (a) Hardness of CNT/Ni nanocomposites, (b) stress-strain curves of CNT/Ni nanocomposites.

3. CNT/Metal Nanocomposites for Field Emission Display Applications

The CNT-implanted Co nanocomposite field emitter is fabricated from CNT/Co nanocomposite powders by a screen printing process, and followed

by a sintering process as shown in Fig. 6(a). The CNT/Co nanocomposite powders mixed with organic binder are screen printed on a ITO substrate (Fig.6(b)) and the organic binder phase is thermally decomposed during the sintering process (Fig.6(c)). The Co nanoparticles are sintered together and form a dense metallic thin film layer, in which the CNTs are implanted, during the sintering of CNT/Co nanocomposite powders. At the same time, the CNTs are straightened and aligned perpendicular to the substrate during the sintering process so that they stand upright on the surface of metallic layer as shown in Fig.6(d). The CNTs tend to be aligned perpendicular to the substrate because the base of the CNT is implanted in the Co metal layer.

Fig. 6 Schematic depiction of fabrication process of CNT/Co nanocomposite field emitters. (a) Cross-sectional SEM image of screen-printed necklace type CNT/Co powders with an organic binder, (b) SEM image showing Co nanoparticles threaded by a straight CNT after sintering and (c) SEM images of the CNT-implanted Co nanocomposite emitter after sintering.

CNT/Co nanocomposite field emitter, fabricated by sintering of CNT/Co nanocomposite powders, shows excellent field emission properties with low

turn-on field of 1.28 V/ μm , high current density of 4.5 mA/cm² at 3 V/ μm and homogeneous field emission as shown in Fig.7. The enhanced field emission properties were due to low electrical resistivity by good interfacial bonding between CNTs and Co and homogeneous dispersion of CNTs in Co matrix [7].

Fig.7 Field emission curves of 60vol.% CNT/Co and 30vol.% CNT/Co nanocomposite field emitters [7].

4. CNT/Polymer Nanocomposites for Organic Solar Cell Applications

The CNT/poly-3-hexylthiophene (P3HT)/ [6,6]-Phenyl C₆₁ butyric acid methyl ester (PCBM) nanocomposites are fabricated for photo-active layer in organic solar cell. Dispersion of CNTs in P3HT/PCBM matrix is the key issue for photo-active layer in organic solar cell application. In general, P3HT/PCBM is soluble in hydrophobic organic solvents. However, covalent functionalized CNTs by strong acid treatment have carboxylate functional groups, it reveals that hydrophilic property. Hydrophilic carboxylate functionalized CNTs are rarely dispersed with large bundling in hydrophobic solvents as shown in Fig.8(a). On the other hand, hydrophobic alkyl-amide functionalized CNTs show homogeneous dispersion with debundling states in organic solvents (Fig.8(b)) compared to carboxylate CNTs. CNT/P3HT/PCBM nanocomposite was used for photo-active layer of organic solar cell as shown Fig.9(a). Power conversion efficiency of organic solar cell with hydrophobic alkyl-amide functionalized CNT/P3HT/PCBM nanocomposites showed 30%

enhancement compared to using raw P3HT/PCBM. The increase of power conversion efficiency is mainly originated from increase of short circuit current due to effective charge collection of high conductive CNTs. However, carboxylate functionalized CNT shows the very low power conversion efficiency like short-circuit behavior. It is originated from large agglomeration of CNTs in hydrophobic P3HT/PCBM matrix.

Fig.8 SEM images of dispersion states of CNTs in organic solvent (chlorobenzene). a) Carboxylate CNTs (hydrophilic) and b) alkyl-amide CNTs (hydrophobic).

Fig.9 (a) Structure of CNT/P3HT/PCBM nanocomposite and (b) I-V curves of organic solar cell using CNT/P3HT/PCBM nanocomposite.

5. CNT/Carbon Nanocomposites for Energy Applications

Mesoporous carbons, with their more accessible porous infrastructure, are promising materials as it is known that pore sizes in the range of 3~5 nm are required to maximize the capacitance in the electric double-layer capacitors. Accordingly, our strategy to

obtain mesoporous carbon materials without using template method is using natural polymer, starch. Starch has a natural ability to assemble into a nanoscale lamellar structure consisting of alternating layers of crystalline phase composed of amylopectin and amorphous phase composed of amylose (Fig.10(a)). Starch can be converted into mesoporous carbonaceous material with an average pore diameter of 6nm similar to the average distance between crystalline layers of native starch. Commercial soluble starch is used as a source of mesoporous carbon nanofibers through electrospinning process (Fig.10(b)). Moreover, mesoporous carbon nanofiber web can provide high surface area, easy access of ions, and binder-free electrode due to its free-standing shape. Embedded or protruded CNTs act as a strong reinforcement and high conductive path to enhance the mechanical and electrical properties of mesoporous carbon nanofibers.

Fig.10 (a) Schematic depiction of lamellar structure of starch granule and (b) schematic depiction of CNT/carbon nanofiber web consisting of mesoporous carbon nanofibers reinforced with CNTs.

Fig.11 Morphology of porous CNT/Carbon nanocomposite fibers. (a) SEM image and (b) TEM image.

By using the natural ability of starch lamellar structure and controlling the carbonization temperature, we successfully fabricated binder-free electrochemical capacitor electrode material consisting of highly mesoporous carbon nanofibers reinforced with CNTs with higher specific capacitance (46 F/g) and electrical conductivity (2.1 S/cm) than other carbon electrodes derived from synthetic polymers and free-standing CNT electrodes. In case of Li-ion battery anode, the first charge capacity of CNT/Carbon nanocomposite showed specific capacity of 510 mAh/g and good cycle performance after 30 cycles, which is significantly higher than that of graphite. The high electrochemical properties of highly mesoporous carbon nanofibers electrode reinforced with CNTs comes from the high specific surface area and the sufficient pore distributions at effective mesoporous sizes of 3~5 nm. Therefore, this material can broaden its application areas into electrodes for supercapacitor, Li-ion battery, catalysis and hydrogen storage.

Fig.12 Electrochemical properties of porous CNT/Carbon nanocomposite fibers.

6. Conclusions

The molecular level mixing process was developed to fabricate CNT nanocomposites with homogeneous dispersion of CNTs and strong interfacial bonding between CNTs and matrices, which are the critical issues on CNT nanocomposites. The CNT nanocomposites with homogeneous dispersion of CNTs, fabricated by molecular level mixing process, showed highly enhanced mechanical properties by effective load transfer from CNTs to matrices. The CNT nanocomposites also showed excellent field emission, optoelectronic and electrochemical properties by low electrical resistivity and good interfacial bonding between CNTs and the matrices. It is expected that CNT nanocomposites can be applied to not only structural applications but also functional applications such as photo-active layer for organic solar cells, electrodes for supercapacitor and Li-ion battery.

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7. References

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